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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITY LINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождидинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifikhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	

FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev	
Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS.....	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov	
S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich	
Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	
PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Bohtaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA:	

AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Xazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
ITHE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliyo Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadilloevna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibodulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	302
Kamola Saidova	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Сайтмуратов Сайтмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT.....	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	

FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST RATE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Seitnazarov Daniyar Bakhadyrovich	
METHODOLOGY AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	385
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF TRANSFORMATION	391
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	395
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ РЕГИОНОВ КАК ФАКТОР ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	399
Бутаева Сабина Холиёровна	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES IN INCREASING THE BRAND CAPITAL OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES	404
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECT FINANCING UNDER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP)	416
Shodiev Akmal O'ktamjon ugli	
IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT	422
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
BLOCKCHAIN AND IOT FOR DIGITAL TRACKING OF FOOD EXPORTIMPORT FLOWS.....	426
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna	
Najmiddinov Yakhyo Fazliddin ugli	

THE PAYBACK PERIOD METHOD IN PERSONAL FINANCE: APPLICATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	438
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADAPTIVE FIBONACCI STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS MODEL FOR GOLD TRADING: EVIDENCE FROM THE XAU/USD MARKET	447
Tukmirzaev Kamol Mumin ugli	
DEVELOPING MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL TRADE THROUGH A BRAND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: DIRECTIONS AND STRATEGIC PRIORITIES.....	455
Shohboz Ro‘zimatov Hamdambek o‘g‘li	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	461
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	466
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ НАУЧНЫХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ НА РОЛЬ СФЕРЫ УСЛУГ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	472
Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FOR UZBEKISTAN’S RURAL DIGITALIZATION: LESSONS FROM THE SPATIAL SPILLOVER EFFECTS OF CHINA’S DIGITAL ECONOMY	481
Zhang Zhe	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ	487
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING SERVICE INFRASTRUCTURE EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM KASHKADARYA REGION	493
Azimov Islom	
ASSESSING DIGITAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	498
Berdiyev Temurbek Makhmudullo ugli	
РАЗРАБОТКА ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ИНДЕКСА КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ (CGI) ДЛЯ БАНКОВ С ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ УЧАСТИЕМ.....	506
Жумадуллаева Дурдона Шухрат кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY-BASED GOVERNANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: LEVERAGING AI AND DATA FOR IMPROVED INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE	512
Olimjonov Abbosjon Olimjonovich	
THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT ON NATIONAL ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	522
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE ESSENCE, TASKS, AND INTERNATIONAL APPROACHES OF INTERNAL AUDIT IN LEASING TRANSACTIONS.....	536
Sadritdinov Bakhodir Bakhtiyarovich	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN THE MINING SECTOR.....	543
Oybekova S.K.	
METHODOLOGY FOR REFLECTING GOODWILL, INTANGIBLE ASSETS, AND INVESTMENTS IN CONSOLIDATION.....	548
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY:	

CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	554
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
THE DMED INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A FOUNDATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL E-HEALTH SYSTEM	561
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN GLOBAL MARKETS	566
Safarova Muxabbat Radjabovna	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SUPPLY SYSTEM OF NURSERY FARMS	573
Abdufarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TOURISM MARKET AND ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PLATFORM ECONOMY.....	580
Jumayev Bobomurod Nurmaxmat o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ «ЖЕНСКОГО» ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ.....	586
Холбаева Сабина Рустамовна	
ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЁТОМ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В МАЛОМ И СРЕДНЕМ БИЗНЕСЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	595
Камбарова Шахнозахон Мирвахитовна	
ISSUES OF EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	603
Umaraliyev Sarvar Rustamovich	
TERRITORIAL DISPROPORTIONS IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE JIZZAKH REGION AND THEIR IMPACT ON TOURIST FLOWS.....	610
A.Sh. Daliev	
T.Sh. Muxiddinov	
METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO HOUSING CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP MECHANISMS.....	616
Mirumar Abdulla Ugli Usmonov	
IMPROVEMENT OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS IN THE FISHERY INDUSTRY: PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE ADAPTATION OF IFRS, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG REPORTING FOR FISHERY CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	620
Shodiev Aslam Rakhmatilloevich	
Alikulov Abdumumin Ismatovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP FRUIT PROCESSING ENTERPRISES BASED ON THE CLUSTER SYSTEM	627
Yusufova Laylo G'ayrat qizi	
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN BANKING SERVICE DEVELOPMENT	635
Mamutova Ayygul Kalmurzaevna	
IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED AUDIT TECHNIQUES (CAATS) AND ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES IN THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS.....	642
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND THE FORMATION OF KEY AUDIT MATTERS (ISA 701)	649
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	656
Abdullayev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN SERICULTURE DEVELOPMENT: ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS APPLICABLE TO UZBEKISTAN.....	664
Janikulova Lobar Shakarbaevna	
SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE THROUGH ESG AND ENERGY MANAGEMENT: A GREEN MARKETING PERSPECTIVE	670
Khaydarova Kamola Axinjanovna	
SYSTEM AND STRATEGY FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN AN ORGANIZATION	675
Azimov Tolmas Nematullayevich	

SYSTEM AND STRATEGY FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN AN ORGANIZATION

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Abstract. This article examines the system of human capital development and its socio-economic orientation. In addition to the set of participants and their interactions, the human capital development system includes the external environment, specific integration mechanisms that strengthen cooperation among participants, and an adaptation mechanism that serves as the basis for the system's stability and self-development.

Keywords: economic entities, human capital development, educational environment, income dynamics, vocational training, professional skills.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается система развития человеческого капитала и её социально-экономическая направленность. Помимо совокупности участников и их взаимодействий, система развития человеческого капитала включает внешнюю среду, определённые интеграционные механизмы, укрепляющие взаимодействие между участниками, а также механизм адаптации, служащий основой устойчивости и саморазвития системы.

Ключевые слова: субъекты хозяйствования, развитие человеческого капитала, образовательная среда, динамика доходов, профессиональное обучение, профессиональные навыки.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of intensifying global economic competition, human capital, encompassing knowledge, skills, and competencies, has become an increasingly important factor in ensuring sustainable economic growth and organizational competitiveness. The development of human capital requires substantial investment. As noted in the literature, "an investment of one dollar in a child's education can generate up to five dollars in lifetime returns. Each additional year of education increases lifetime earnings by an average of 9%, and in some cases by as much as 15%." Therefore, creating favourable conditions for human capital development and prioritizing investment in this form of capital remain among the most pressing issues in the global economy.

Under the conditions of rapid development of the digital economy and artificial intelligence, increasing attention is being devoted worldwide to improving the theoretical and methodological foundations of human capital, unlocking its internal potential, and ensuring the alignment of production and social development with future strategic goals through effective human capital management. Current research primarily focuses on creating decent employment opportunities commensurate with employees' human capital, expanding opportunities for human capital development within enterprise management, and improving the organizational and economic mechanisms for human capital development in the context of economic transformation.

In Uzbekistan, comprehensive measures are being implemented to fundamentally improve the quality of human capital, enhance the quality of education, and promote innovative approaches to supporting human capital in production sectors under the conditions of economic digitalization. Significant progress has also been achieved in improving the utilization of human capital within textile and light industry enterprises. As emphasized by the country's leadership, "the textile industry is the sector that has created the largest number of jobs and provides employment for the greatest share of the population among industrial sectors. In 2023, the production volume of textile and apparel products reached UZS 94 trillion, representing a 4.2-fold increase over

the past seven years, while exports amounted to USD 3.1 billion. Currently, more than 6,000 enterprises in the textile industry provide permanent employment for approximately 570,000 people.”

In this regard, further research is required to improve the system of human capital development in line with long-term strategic objectives, examine the role of labour productivity in the process of human capital development, substantiate effective approaches to human capital development under transformational conditions, and enhance the institutional and organizational framework for the efficient utilization of human capital.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The transformation of human capital development, encompassing such essential dimensions as employee training, professional development, and employers' responsibility for employees' health and well-being, constitutes a fundamental prerequisite for improving organizational performance. Particularly under conditions of digital transformation, the enhancement of systems for the formation, development, and effective utilization of human capital remains a central focus of economic research.

The theoretical foundations of human capital, its development, and its effective utilization have been extensively explored in the works of prominent economists, including A. Smith, M. Friedman, D. Ricardo, T. Schultz, I. Fisher, G. Becker, and L. Walras¹. Their studies established the conceptual basis for understanding human capital as a critical driver of economic growth and productivity.

Among scholars from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), significant contributions to the study of human capital development have been made by L. V. Brik, Y. G. Odegov, V. V. Papyan, A. I. Dobrynin, and Y. M. Nikiforova², whose research emphasizes the organizational and socio-economic dimensions of human capital management.

In Uzbekistan, substantial scientific contributions to the study of human capital formation and development have been made by Q. Kh. Abdurakhmonov, B. Kh. Umurzakov, N. Q. Zokirova, N. Kh. Rakhimova, Z. Y. Khudoyberdiyev, G. Q. Abdurakhmonova, N. U. Arabov, D. A. Nasimov, and Sh. D. Qudbiyev³. Their research has significantly advanced the theoretical and practical understanding of human capital development within the national economy.

It should be emphasized that comprehensive studies addressing the global challenges of human capital development transformation have been conducted primarily by the Uzbek academician Q. Kh. Abdurakhmonov, whose work represents one of the most systematic approaches to this field.

The determinants of labour productivity and the selection of appropriate performance indicators under conditions of economic growth have been extensively investigated by F. Cunha, J. Heckman, L. Lochner, D. Masterov, R. Ahmad, N. Angrist, S. Djankov, P. Goldberg, P. Stevens, M. Weale, B. Bosworth, and S. Collins. Their studies provide important methodological foundations for evaluating the contribution of human capital to economic performance.

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Умурзаков Б.Х. ва б. *Меҳнат ресурслари шаклланиши ва тақсимланишининг ҳудудий усуллари* / Монография. –Т.: “Lesson Press”, 2017 й. -184 б.; Abdurahmonov Q.X., Zokirova N.Q. *Mehnat iqtisodiyoti va sotsiologiyasi. O'quv qo'llanma*. –Т.: “Fan va texnologiya”, 2013y. -536b.; Rakhimova N.X. *Роль и место женщины на рынке труда Узбекистана. Теория и практика*. – Т.: “Fan”, 2006г.; Худойбердиев З.Я. ва б. *Тадбиркорлик ва ишга жойлаштириш технологияси асослари*. 2-нашр. *Ўқув қўлланма*. –Т.: “ILM ZIYO”, 2017й. -344 б.; Абдурахмонова Г.Қ. *Инсон ресурсларини бошқариш*. Дарслик. –Т.: ЎзР ФА “Фан” нашриёти давлат корхонаси, 2021. – 696б.; Арабов Н.У. *Ўзбекистон Республикасида меҳнат бозори инфратузилмасини ривожлантириш самарадорлигини ошириш*. Монография. – Т.: “Fan va texnologiyalar” нашриёти, 2017й. -336 б.; Насимов Д.А. *Иқтисодиётнинг инновацион ривожланиши шароитида иш билан бандлик эгилувчанлигини таъминлаш механизмларини такомиллаштириш*. Монография. –Т.: “Fan va texnologiya”, 2018. -260б.; Кудбиев Ш.Д. *Методологические основы трансформации рынка труда в развитии цифровой экономики*. Монография. – Т.: «Innovatsion rivojlanish nashriyot-matbaa uyi» ДУК, 2020. – 178 с.

Despite these valuable contributions, the problems of human capital development in the digital economy—particularly through employee training, professional skill enhancement, and strengthening employers' responsibility for occupational health as mechanisms for increasing labour income—have not yet been comprehensively examined. Furthermore, methodological and conceptual approaches to these issues remain insufficiently developed, creating a need for further theoretical, methodological, and empirical research⁴.

The growing popularity of the human capital development concept in contemporary socio-economic research reflects the search for new scientific paradigms capable of explaining the evolving patterns of economic activity. Traditional neoclassical economic theory, which is primarily focused on market equilibrium, does not always adequately explain the dynamics of socio-economic systems, institutional structures, or scientific and production cycles under conditions of rapid technological change and scientific advancement.

The shift in analytical emphasis from individual economic agents toward complex socio-economic systems necessitates the reconsideration of many theoretical approaches within economics. A systems approach provides a comprehensive analytical framework for examining the interrelationships among socio-economic phenomena within a unified research environment⁵.

Accordingly, the human capital development system should be viewed as an integrated paradigm that emphasizes the interdependence and interactions among its structural components. Within this framework, an enterprise's activities related to the formation and development of human capital are considered integral elements of a broader socio-economic system.

The concept of a human capital development system is increasingly applied to the analysis of open systems consisting of numerous heterogeneous participants connected through diverse forms of interaction. Originally developed within the biological sciences, the ecosystem concept has subsequently been adopted in other disciplines to explain the evolution of relationships among system participants and their interactions with the surrounding environment.

From this perspective, the human capital development system may be regarded as a specific socio-economic ecosystem. Although no universally accepted definition of a socio-economic ecosystem currently exists, the definition proposed by G. B. Kleiner appears to be among the most comprehensive. According to Kleiner, a socio-economic ecosystem is a territorially localized socio-economic entity comprising interacting independent economic, social, or organizational actors and their groups, together with a population of products or outcomes capable of independent functioning, whose long-term development is sustained through the circulation of material, informational, energy, and other resources. This approach places particular emphasis on the simultaneous coexistence of cooperation and competition among ecosystem participants.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a systematic and interdisciplinary research approach to examine the human capital development system within organizations. The research is based on system analysis, comparative analysis, and synthesis of theoretical and empirical literature on human capital management. Scientific publications, monographs, national policy documents, and international studies were reviewed to identify the key components, participants, and mechanisms of human capital development. In addition, the systems approach was applied to analyze the interactions among educational institutions, enterprises, and the external environment. The findings were interpreted using logical analysis and generalization to formulate recommendations for improving human capital development strategies in organizations under the conditions of digital transformation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The human capital development system should not be equated solely with the educational environment or professional education. If the "human capital development space" of an enterprise comprises several organizations that are not directly interconnected, it should be regarded as an established organizational structure based on the functional relationships among the participants involved in the human capital development process.

In addition to the participants and their interrelationships, the human capital development system includes the surrounding environment, integration mechanisms that facilitate interaction among stakeholders, and adaptation mechanisms that ensure the system's sustainability and continuous self-development.

4 Jarvi K., Almpantopoulou A., Ritala P. Organization of knowledge ecosystem: prefigurative and partial forms // Research Policy. 2018. No. 47(8). P. 1523–1537.

5 Moore J.F. Predators and prey: a new ecology of competition. Harvard Business Review, 1993, May-June, P. 75–86

The human capital development system initially emerged as an educational ecosystem designed to address the growing demand for engineers possessing modern knowledge, advanced professional competencies, and the ability to master innovative technologies, materials, and contemporary technological and testing equipment. This need became particularly significant in response to workforce ageing and the natural retirement of highly qualified specialists, which intensified the challenge of maintaining an adequately skilled engineering workforce.

From a systems perspective, the principal characteristics of the human capital development system include its strategic orientation, expected outputs, diversity of participants and their interactions, environmental conditions and their influence on the system, as well as mechanisms of self-organization and continuous development.

Identifying these fundamental characteristics makes it possible to determine the specific features, existing limitations, and future development prospects of the system. The primary objective of any human capital development system is to ensure sustainable organizational performance and continuous growth in enterprise income through the effective utilization of human resources.

Within the context of this study, the main objective of the human capital development system is to provide enterprises with a continuous supply of qualified personnel, ranging from skilled workers to highly specialized engineers.

Whereas the primary output of a biological ecosystem is biomass, the principal outcome of a human capital development system is human capital itself. As noted earlier, human capital broadly encompasses knowledge, abilities, professional skills, competencies, work experience, motivation, and labour potential that enable individuals to generate economic value and earn income.

Human capital represents the most valuable strategic resource of an enterprise, surpassing physical capital in importance. Unlike physical assets, human capital activates productive resources and, more importantly, generates innovation through the creation of new technologies, products, and organizational solutions.

The reproduction of enterprise human capital, including both its formation and continuous development, is carried out by participants within the professional and educational ecosystem. These stakeholders collectively contribute to developing the competencies required for sustainable organizational growth.

Within the human capital development system examined in this study, the key participants include general secondary schools, vocational education institutions, higher education institutions, continuing professional education providers, and the structural divisions of enterprises themselves.

Similar to biological ecosystems, the human capital development system can be conceptualized as comprising three interconnected levels corresponding to its functional objectives.

General secondary education institutions constitute the foundation of the system by preparing prospective students for subsequent stages of human capital development.

Vocational education institutions prepare skilled workers and technical personnel who may either continue their education at higher education institutions or directly enter the labour market. These institutions play a critical role in supplying enterprises with qualified specialists. Furthermore, the establishment of integrated educational platforms between universities and enterprises provides the basis for developing a workforce equipped with specialized knowledge and practical competencies. Collectively, the first two levels are responsible for forming human capital in accordance with enterprise requirements.

The enterprise itself represents the final stage of the system by employing graduates of vocational and higher education institutions, as well as participants in continuing professional education programmes. In accordance with organizational requirements and regulatory standards, enterprises further develop employees' competencies through workplace learning and continuous professional development. Consequently, this third level contributes to human capital development not only through formal training programmes but also through knowledge sharing, professional collaboration, and practical work experience, thereby enriching employees' competencies and enhancing organizational effectiveness.

It should be emphasized that, within the human capital development system, the coordinated efforts of all participants generate synergistic effects that contribute to the qualitative enhancement of human capital. These effects are reflected in the acquisition of professional knowledge and competencies, the accumulation of practical experience, the expansion of professional capacity, and the development of communication skills. The effectiveness of interactions among participants within the human capital development system, as well as its capacity for self-governance, largely depends on the level of collaboration and the organizational culture that supports cooperative relationships (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Human Capital Development System⁶

An integral component of any human capital development system is the environment in which it operates. This environment encompasses a range of external factors, including the socio-economic conditions of the region, the level of industrial development, and the effectiveness of the education system. These environmental conditions significantly influence the functioning and long-term sustainability of the human capital development system.

Furthermore, the operating environment of the human capital development system is subject to external changes that may affect its conditions of functioning. Such external influences constitute environmental factors that shape the system’s performance and require continuous adaptation to ensure its resilience, sustainability, and capacity for further development (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Traditional Concept of Human Capital Development⁷

6 author’s development
7 author’s development

In studying the human capital development system, it is also important to take into account its process of self-development. The self-development of society can be described within a socio-economic system based on market principles and laws.

Based on the above considerations, at the current stage of human capital development, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms for transferring professional knowledge within the system.

Improving the effectiveness of the human capital development system can be achieved only when three essential components are closely interconnected:

clear requirements established by enterprises regarding the knowledge and skills of specialists;

the adequacy of knowledge and competencies formed in general secondary, vocational, and higher education institutions;

effective educational approaches that meet the requirements of a post-industrial society.

At the same time, when enterprises define requirements for employees' knowledge and skills, educational institutions are expected to ensure that the competencies they develop correspond to these requirements. The development of effective educational methods is the result of close cooperation between enterprises and educational institutions. In general, the outcomes of the human capital development system depend on the dynamics of complex relationships among its participants within the socio-economic environment during the process of human capital formation.

The self-development process of the human capital development system is based on increasing structural complexity and enhancing adaptability to changing external conditions through continuous renewal.

The main characteristics of the human capital development system can be summarized as follows:

System objective: the continuous provision of enterprises with qualified personnel;

System output/result: human capital;

System participants: general secondary schools, vocational and higher education institutions, enterprises and their structural units;

System environment: the socio-economic conditions of the region and the level of development of the education sector;

Self-development process of the system: manifested in the increasing integration between educational institutions and enterprises, as well as in the continuous improvement of teaching methods and approaches.

The model illustrating the relationship between human capital and enterprise performance consists of several key elements. Investment in general human capital includes training, education, knowledge, and skills that enhance the efficiency and productivity of human capital (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Concept of Human Capital Development in Enterprises⁸

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Human capital refers not only to knowledge, skills, and competencies, but also to those capabilities that are currently used or may be used in the future to generate income for an enterprise. At the same time, it should be emphasized that there is no direct linear relationship between investment in education and the return on such investment, since the overall cultural, economic, and organizational characteristics of an enterprise, as well as individual employee attributes, play a crucial role in determining the effective application of acquired knowledge in organizational processes. An investment-based approach to the components of intellectual capital requires an assessment of investment efficiency in the development of different types of capital, based on a comparison between investment costs and the resulting returns.

⁸ author's development

In the context of the ongoing digital transformation in Uzbekistan, the following conclusions and recommendations can be drawn from the conducted research on the transformation of human capital development:

Currently, among researchers studying human capital in the country, there is a tendency to use the concepts of “human factor,” “investment in humans,” and “human capital” interchangeably. However, these terms have distinct conceptual meanings and specific areas of application. In academic research, it is essential to use each term accurately and consistently. In particular, the term “human capital” should continue to be used in its internationally accepted meaning. The present study examines the necessity, innovative tools and methods, as well as the socio-economic significance of the transformation of human capital development.

The issue of human capital development transformation and the associated challenges represents one of the most relevant topics for countries undergoing industrial and innovation-driven transformation. Moreover, reforms aimed at developing key human capital infrastructure sectors, particularly education and healthcare, require active engagement from all stakeholders in addressing human capital development challenges. In this context, the theoretical foundations and innovative approaches to human capital development transformation have been explored.

It has been scientifically substantiated that, in the process of innovative human capital transformation, both direct and indirect interactions between investment in education, skills, and experience, as well as investment in healthcare, significantly influence labour productivity and overall efficiency.

The impact of human capital development transformation on enterprise-level practical activities has been empirically confirmed through the analysis of survey data using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach. The results demonstrate that human capital development is closely associated with employee training, knowledge enhancement, professional skill improvement, acquisition of practical competencies, and accumulation of work experience.

As a logical outcome of successful educational reforms in the country, it is necessary to ensure employment opportunities for highly educated and qualified human resources, which represent the most active and valuable segment of human capital, by creating modern job positions that correspond to their knowledge, competencies, and skills. In this regard, greater attention should be paid at the state level to aligning labour market demand with graduates’ competencies.

Finally, while the volume of investment in a specific type of capital within an enterprise can be relatively easily quantified, significant challenges arise in measuring the contribution of each element of intellectual capital to the overall growth of enterprise value.

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